

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

PRELIMINARY QUALITATIVE SCREENING, PHYSICOCHEMICAL STANDARDIZATION AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF A HERBO MINERAL SIDDHA FORMULATION GANDHAGA KARUPPU

D. Deepa Bai^{1,2}, Ashima Joshi^{1,2}, Geeta Tyagi^{1,2}, V. Vijaya Kumar¹, S. C. Verma*¹, M. B. Shankar¹

¹Pharmacopoeia Commission for Indian Medicine and Homoeopathy, Kamala Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad, 201002. Uttar Pradesh, India.

²Central Council for Research in Siddha, Chennai-106.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 05/07/2017

Available online
02/08/2017

Keywords

Standardization,
Gandhaga Karuppu,
AYUSH,
Authenticate,
Traditional Siddha Medicine,
Antimicrobial Activity.

ABSTRACT

A recent resurgence of interest in the traditional systems like AYUSH (Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha & Homoeopathy) systems of Indian Medicine is due to the fact that these systems are natural/ environmental friendly/ biodegradable. The safety based efficacy of these medicines is also equally important because of the issues of adulteration and substitution and contamination and for globalization too. Therefore, the development of pharmacopoeial standards becomes mandatory as emphasized by WHO. Under the Law of drugs and cosmetic act 1940, quality control and analytical standardization of ASU&H drugs in the light of phytochemical aspects geared up in India. Scientist's (silver bullet) method of extracting the chemical to target the effect led to suggestion that most drugs are devoid of activity which may due to the in-vitro methods and lack of solubility of the drug. This paves way to support traditional formulations, where drug parts are added as such and processed and the finished product administered with suitable adjuvants (Gunshot method to treat the individual as a whole). The objective of the present study to evaluate the organoleptic characters, acid and basic radicals, pH, phytochemicals, standardize physico chemically to authenticate the sulphur based classical Siddha formulation Gandhaga karuppu and also to evaluate the antimicrobial activity. The Results revealed, the presence of sulphate, chloride, carbonate, fluoride and iron and ammonium, acidic pH, no significant antimicrobial activity, higher acid insoluble ash values which might be due to higher mineral content present in the finished product. The Organoleptic characters and other physicochemical values signify the good quality and purity of the herbo-mineral drug Gandhaga karuppu.

*Corresponding author

Dr. S. C. Verma, *Dr. D. Deepa Bai

Principal Scientist

Pharmacopoeia Commission for Indian Medicine and Homoeopathy,

Kamala Nehru Nagar, Ghaziabad, 201002.

scvpharma@gmail.com

*Senior Research Fellow (Siddha)

deepasiddhaa@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Dr. D. Deepa Bai et al. Preliminary Qualitative Screening, Physicochemical Standardization And Antimicrobial Activity Of A Herbo Mineral Siddha Formulation Gandhaga Karuppu. . Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2017:7(07).**

Copy right © 2017 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization estimates that about 80% of the populations living in the developing countries rely almost exclusively on traditional medicine for their primary health care needs [1]. Herbal medicines were in great demand in the developed as well as in developing countries for primary health care because of their wide biological and medicinal activities, higher safety margin, and lower costs [2]. The Siddha system is practiced in Tamil Nadu since antiquity. But the scientific evidence to prove the rationale of using these formulations in health care is not well established. To widen the selection of traditional remedies globally and to make the expectation of 'well health' of humanity more reasonable, all the drugs are to be standardized, pertaining to the Laws of regulation by the AYUSH Ministry, Government of India. Since adulteration and substitution remain challenging, scientific documentation becomes essential for the reference standards and so, the present study is to standardize the Siddha classical compound formulation Gandaka karuppu (GK)[3] and correlate it clinically since solubility of the Sulphur remains challenging and discuss it with the anti microbial activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Formulation Composition

Gandhagam (Sulphur) and four Plant drugs mentioned in the Table below serve as ingredients of the Siddha formulation

Procurement and authentication of drugs

The raw drugs were procured from raw drug store from local market of Chennai, India. The identity and authenticity of the drugs were confirmed by Dr. M. Allimuthu, Professor and HOD, Department of Gunapadam, Govt. Siddha Medical College, Arumbakkam, Chennai.

'Suddhi' (Purification) of Crude drug ingredients of Gandaga karuppu

Table.1 Method of Purification of Crude drug ingredients of Gandaga karuppu.

S No	Crude drug ingredients	Part used	Method of Purification
1	Sulphur	The market crude drug	Melted with clarified butter in an iron pan and poured through a clean muslin cloth into cow's (<i>Bos taurus indicus</i>) milk. The process is repeated thrice. The obtained sulphur is then soaked in, 1. Fresh juice of Azhavanam <i>Lawsonia inermis</i> L. (Fam. Lythraceae) 2. Katthazhai (Syn. Kariyabolam) <i>Aloe barbadensis</i> Mill. Syn. <i>Aloe vera</i> Tourn. ex L. (Fam. Liliaceae) and 3. Sour skimmed milk of Cow (<i>Bos taurus indicus</i>) Outer coat peeled off.
2	Chukku (Dry Ginger) <i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc. (Fam. Zingiberaceae)	Dried rhizome	
3	Milaku- Black Pepper <i>Piper nigrum</i> L. (Fam. Piperaceae)	Fully mature dried fruit	Immature pin head sized fruits are thrown off. Roasted slightly.
4	Thippili- Long pepper <i>Piper longum</i> L. (Fam. Piperaceae)	Dried, immature, catkin-like fruits with bracts	Immature pin head sized fruits are thrown off. Roasted slightly.
5	Vasambu- Sweet flag <i>Acorus calamus</i> Linn. (Fam. Araceae)	Dried rhizome	Washed and dried under shade.

Preparation of the test drug

100gms of purified Sulphur is taken. The ingredients of the chooranam are powdered separately and taken in the specified ratio mentioned below and mixed well.

Dried ginger - 200gms

Pepper – 15gms

Long pepper- 15gms

Sweet flag- 15 gms

Half of the chooranam is taken in an earthen vessel above which the sulphur cake is placed. The remaining half of the chooranam is put over and around the sulphur. The vessel is closed by another earthen vessel and made air tight by 'Seelai seidhal' in which moist mud pasted ghada cloth (thick cotton cloth) is wrapped in 7 whorls at the rim of the two pots holding them tight. The apparatus is subjected to 'Pudam' with 15 'varatties' (cowdung cakes). Pudam is the process of heating in which the purified raw drug or the pellet (for parpam or chenduram) or the apparatus which should undergo the heat (or burning) is placed in the centre and the arrangement of cowdung cakes is done around it as if it is embedded within the specified fuel mentioned in that particular classical text such that equal heat is rendered on all sides. The heating process is done in a pit. Care should be taken that the cakes should not get burnt but should provide heat in a flame enough to provide constant heat and should not evolve much smoke too. The blackish remnant obtained is collected, grinded to a fine powder and stored in air tight glass container. To be administered with Cow's ghee.

Analytical specification of Karuppu

Karuppu simulate centuram. So the analytical specifications are applicable for karuppu preparations and was done as per the protocol for testing published by AYUSH[4].

Table.2 Analytical specifications for Karuppu.

S No	Analytical Specifications for Karuppu
1	Description, Colour, Odour
2	Identification
3	Particle size. Mesh size 200-300
4	Loss on drying at 105° C
5	Total ash
6	Acid insoluble ash
7	Water soluble ash
8	Assay of element(s)
9	Assay of element(s)
10	Siddha specifications
	Lustreless
	Fine enough to enter the crevices of finger
	Floats on water Smokeless
	Tasteless
	Irreversible

Organoleptic characteristics

Sensory parameters like colour, odour, taste, size of the particles were analyzed and recorded.

Physico Chemical Characterization

All the physicochemical parameters were carried out as per standard guidelines [5, 6]. Additionally pH was done at 25°C (1:10 Ratio).

Determination of total ash

About 2 grams of the dried crude drug were weighed accurately in a tarred platinum or silica dish and was incinerated at a temperature not exceeding 550°c until free from carbon. It was then cooled and weighed. The percentage of ash was calculated with reference to air dried drug.

Determination of water soluble ash

The total ash was boiled for five minutes with 25ml of water. The insoluble matter was collected on a Gooch crucible (or) an ash less filter paper. It was washed with hot water and ignited for 15 minutes, at a temperature not exceeding 550°c. The weight of the insoluble matter was subtracted from the weight of the ash, the difference in the weight of the ash represents the water soluble ash. The percentage of water soluble ash was calculated with reference to the dried drug.

Determination of acid insoluble ash

The total ash was boiled with 25ml of 2 M HCL for 15 minutes. The insoluble matter was collected on a Gooch crucible (or) an ash less filter paper. It was washed with hot water and ignited. It was then cooled in a desiccators and weighed. The percentage of acid insoluble ash was calculated with reference to the dried drug.

Loss on drying

5gm of the drug is heated in a hot oven at 40 degree C to constant weight. The percentage of loss of weight was calculated.

Qualitative analysis for presence of acid and basic radicals (Raman 2006)[7].

Preparation of extract

5gm of Gandaka karuppu is weighed accurately and placed in a 250ml clean beaker and added with 50 ml of distilled water. It is then boiled well for about 20 minutes. Then it is covered and filtered in a 100ml volumetric flask and made up to 100 ml with distilled water.

The aqueous extract was used for the analysis of acid radicals, basic radicals.

Test for acid radicals

Test for sulphate

2 ml of the above prepared extract is taken in a test tube. To this, 2 ml of 4 % ammonium oxalate solution is added. Cloudy appearance/ white precipitate indicate the presence of sulphate.

2ml of Sodium carbonate extract is added with 2 ml of dilute hydrochloric acid until the effervescence ceases off. 2ml of Barium chloride solution is then added. A white precipitate insoluble in concentrated Hydrochloric acid confirm the presence of sulphate.

Test for Chloride

2 ml of Sodium carbonate extract is added with dilute nitric acid till the effervescence ceases. Then 2 ml of silver nitrate solution is added. Appearance of cloudy white precipitate completely soluble in excess of Ammonium hydroxide solution indicates the presence of chloride.

Test for Phosphate

2ml of the extract is treated with 2 ml of ammonium molybdate solution and 2 ml of concentrated Nitric acid. Appearance of yellow precipitate / cloudy appearance with yellow colour indicates the presence of phosphate.

Test for carbonates

2 ml of the extract is treated with 2 ml of magnesium sulphate solution. Cloudy appearance/white precipitate indicates the presence of carbonates.

Test for Sulphide

1 gm of the substance is treated with 2 ml of concentrated Hydrochloric acid. Colourless rotten egg smelling gas turning lead acetate paper black on warming indicates the presence of sulphide.

Test for Nitrate

1 gm of the substance is heated with copper turning and concentrated sulphuric acid and the test tube is viewed vertically down. Copious evolution of reddish brown gas indicates the presence of nitrate

Test for Fluoride and Oxalate

2 ml of the extract is added with 2 ml of dilute acetic acid and 2 ml of calcium chloride solution and heated. Cloudy appearance/ White precipitate indicate the presence of fluoride/oxalate.

5 drops of clear solution is added with 2ml of dilute sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) and slightly warmed. To this, 1 ml of dilute potassium permanganate solution ($KMnO_4$) is added. Decolourisation of Potassium permanganate solution indicates the presence of oxalate.

Test for Nitrate

3 drops of the extract is placed on a filter paper. On that, 2 drops of acetic acid and 2 drops of benzidine solution is placed. Development of Yellowish red colour confirm the presence of Nitrate.

Test for basic radicals**Test for Lead**

2 ml of the extract is added with 2 ml of Potassium Iodide solution. Yellow precipitate soluble in hot water and reappearing as "Golden Yellow fumes" on cooling indicates the presence of lead.

Test for copper

One pinch of substance is made into paste with concentrated Hydrochloric acid in a watch glass and introduced into the non-luminous part of the flame. Appearance of bluish green coloured flame indicates the presence of copper.

2 ml of the extract is added with excess of Ammonia solution. Bluish precipitate or deep blue coloured solution indicates the presence of copper.

Test for Aluminium

To the 2 ml of the extract Sodium hydroxide solution is added in drops to excess. Appearance of white precipitate soluble in excess of Sodium Hydroxide indicates the presence of aluminium.

Test for Iron

To the 2ml of extract 2ml of Ammonium thiocyanate solution is added. Appearance of blood red colour indicates the presence of Ferric iron.

To the 2 ml of extract 2 ml of Ammonium thiocyanate solution and 2 ml of concentrated Nitric Acid is added. Appearance of blood red colour indicates the presence of Ferric iron.

Test for Zinc

To the 2 ml of extract, sodium hydroxide solution is added in drop of excess. Appearance of white precipitate solution in excess of sodium hydroxide solution indicates the presence of zinc.

Test for Calcium

2 ml of the extract is added with 2 ml of 4 % Ammonium oxalate solution. Cloudy appearance/white precipitate indicates the presence of calcium.

Test for Magnesium

To the 2 ml of the extract sodium hydroxide solution is added in drops to excess. Appearance of white precipitate, insoluble in excess of sodium hydroxide solution indicates the presence of magnesium.

Test for Ammonium

To 2 ml of extract few ml of Nessler's reagent and excess of sodium hydroxide solution are added. Appearance of reddish brown precipitate indicates the presence of ammonium.

Test for Potassium

A pinch of substance is treated with 2 ml of sodium nitrite solution, treated with 2 ml of cobalt nitrite in 30% glacial acetic acid. Appearance of yellowish precipitate indicates the presence of potassium.

Test for Sodium

2 pinches of the substance is made into paste by using Hydrochloric acid and introduced into the blue flame. Appearance of yellow colour flame indicates the presence of sodium.

Test for Mercury

2 ml of the extract is treated with 2 ml of Sodium hydroxide solution. Appearance of yellow precipitate indicates the presence of Mercury.

Test for Arsenic

2 ml of extract is treated with 2 ml of silver nitrate solution. Yellow precipitate / brownish precipitate indicates the presence of Arsenic.

Anti microbial study of Gandaka karuppu**Media used**

Nutrient Agar per litre/gram (NA).

Peptone	-5.0	g
Yeast extract	-2.0	g
NaCl	-5.0	g
Agar	-18.0	g
Distilled water	-1000	ml
pH	- 7.0	

Culture collection and maintenance

The organisms used for the study namely, *E.Coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio cholera*, *Pseudomonas spp* were obtained from CAS in Botany and Department of Biochemistry University of Madras, Guindy Campus, Chennai 600 025.

Preparation of culture for antibacterial studies

Twelve hours old bacterial suspension was adjusted to 0.5 OD and 1.0ml from the above was inoculated into 50 ml of nutrient broth and incubated at 37 ° C in an orbital shaker at 150 rpm. To determine the growth rate, culture was removed at 4h interval and the growth was monitored by measuring the optical density at 540nm in spectrophotometer. The growth curve was drawn by plotting OD value against the incubation time.

Antibacterial susceptibility test[8]

Brain heart infusion (BHI) agar was used for susceptibility testing. Disks of 6mm in diameter were punched from a sheet of Whatman filter paper, sterilized, and impregnated with 25 micro L each of 0.2 g/ml extract or solvent alone and dried at 30–35 degree C for 12–24 h. The bacterial inoculums were prepared from subcultures of bacteria as follows: four to five colonies of the isolates were emulsified in sterile distilled water and the turbidity adjusted to 1.5×10⁸ CFU/ml (corresponding to 0.5 McFarland standards). A sterile cotton swab was dipped into the standardized bacterial suspension and used to evenly inoculate the BHI agar plates. The plates were allowed to dry for 3-5 min. Thereafter, all disks were placed on the plates and pressed gently to ensure complete contact with agar. A distance of at least 15mm was maintained from the edges of the plates to prevent overlapping of inhibition zones. Fifteen minutes following placement of the disks, the plates were incubated at 37°C for 2–5 days. They were then examined and the diameter of the zone of inhibition measured.

Well-in agar method[9].

Anti-bacterial activity of aqueous extract of Gandaka karuppu was tested by a modified well-in agar method. The inoculum suspension was spread uniformly over the agar plates using sterile cotton swab spreader, to get a uniform distribution of bacteria. Subsequently, using a sterile borer, well of 0.5 cm diameter was made in the inoculated media. Different concentration drug 25, 50, 75 and 100 µg/ml of each extract was aseptically filled into the well. Later the plates were placed at room temperature for an hour to allow diffusion of extract into the agar. Then the plates were incubated for 24 h at 37°C. The results were recorded by measuring the diameter of inhibition zone at the end of 24 h - 48 h.

RESULTS**Description**

Fine powder and is similar to Centuram but differs from it, in being black in colour.

Table.3. Organoleptic Characters of Ingredients of Gandhaga Karuppu.

Ingredients	Characters of Crude drugs that complied with SPI, API and others*	Characters of Obtained Powdered ingredients
Sulphur	Yellow crystalline lumps with yellowish white streaks, Resinous lusture, brittle, Transluscent	Yellow color, Characteristic Odor, Bitter taste
Chukku	Laterally compressed Rhizome, branched on upper side, each with a depressed scar at the apex	Cream color, and aromatic, agreeable and pungent taste
Black Pepper	Greyish-black to black, hard and wrinkled	Blackish-grey color, aromatic, pungent taste
Thippili	Blackish brown or black, sessile, with small protuberances of minute fruits that are evenly arranged around an axis; surface rough and composite; Hard and brittle, fractured surface not even but granular, shows a central axis and 6 to 12 fruitlets arranged around an axis.	Deep moss green color, pungent taste producing numbness on the tongue; odour aromatic.
Vasambu	Brownish-red or grayish-yellow externally, slightly flattened, rough, branched, upper side marked with alternately arranged, large, broadly, triangular, transverse leaf scars which almost encircle the rhizome, lower side shows elevated tubercular spots of root scars, buff coloured intemally, Hard and brittle, odour, aromatic; taste, pungent and bitter.	Puff color, pungent and bitter taste.

SPI – Siddha Pharmacopoeia of India

API – Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India

* Chinese Medicinal Material data base

Note – No significant difference is observed in the characteristic odour and taste of these crude drugs and respective powders after purification and so these specific characters mentioned in the powder is also applicable to crude drugs.

Organoleptic characters of the finished product Gandhaga karuppu

Black in colour, characteristic odour is due to the ash of sulphur and very slight bitter taste. Complied with the Siddha specifications for centuram. [Table.2.]

Physico chemical characterization**Table.3 Physico chemical analysis of Gandaga karuppu.**

S. No	Physico chemical Parameters	Results
1	pH at 25°C (1:10 Ratio)	5.68
2	Ash Value @ 550°C (%)	16.40
3	Water soluble (%)	4.20
4	Alkalinity as CaCO ₃ in water soluble ash (%)	0.06
5	Acid Insoluble Ash, (%)	55.10
6	Loss of drying @ 105°C (%)	0.52

Table .4 Qualitative chemical analysis of Gandaga karuppu.

S No	Acid radicals	Basic radicals
1	Sulphate	Iron
2	Chloride	Ammonium
3	Carbonate	
4	Fluoride.	

Anti microbial study of Gandaka Karuppu

The antibacterial activity of crude ethanol extract of *Gandaka Karuppu* was tested against various bacterial pathogens and inhibition was determined by disc diffusion method.

Gandaka Karuppu showed no significant inhibition against the test pathogens. This may be due to the problem in the solubility of the drug.

DISCUSSION

Karuppu in Siddha system of medicine is a '*kajjali*' (Ayurvedic dosage form) [10, 11] like black coloured powder. But in Gandaka karuppu the black final product is obtained by the thermal reaction of sulphur with herbal ingredients without mercury. Other karuppu medicines are Sivanar amirtham, Kasthuri karuppu, Pattu karuppu etc. Herbal Karukku medicines are Vasambu karukku, Amai Odu Karukkuk Kudineer, Uthamani karukku etc. Gowri chindamani is a black coloured formulation of Siddha medicine made of mercury and sulphur [12].

The organoleptic characters are the simple and quick evaluatory means for the establishment of identity and the quality and to judge the material in its crude and powder form [13]. The results revealed conceals the fact that the crude drugs used for preparation of formulation lie within the limit which signifies their good quality and purity. The shelf life and stability of a drug depend on the deterioration time and in turn on the amount of water present in the formulation. The higher moisture content deteriorate the formulation due to fungus. Insufficient drying favors the spoilage by molds and bacteria and makes possible the enzymatic destruction of active principles. Apart from the dryness of the drug, the moisture removal rate is also equally important together with the removal condition. If the rate is too slow, much spoilage may occur before the drying process is completed [14]. The loss on drying 0.52 % in the final product signify that the drugs are properly dried and stored. The shelf life for Karuppu is generally 1 year as per Siddha formulary [15] but recently notified to be 2 and 5 yrs based on the sources of ingredients. Since Gandaga karuppu is a herbo mineral drug, the shelf life is 5 yrs amendment [16].

The pH conventionally represents the acidity and alkalinity [17]. The pH value influences the quality of medicine [18] and it controls many chemical and microbiological reactions [19]. Under low pH value (presence of acidic substances), the bacterial count could be low, but at neutral or higher pH, contamination of the herbal preparations could be observed to be higher. This suggests that a neutral or alkaline pH favoured high contamination levels of the herbal preparations [20]. The pH obtained 5.7 indicates that the drug is acidic. This pH from mineral or phytochemicals is emphasized to be evaluated so that clarity regarding the consideration of sulphur alone in the final product or inclusion of the charred churanam part too in the final product, be achieved. The results obtained in this standardization study included the churanam part. The potency is also to be considered regarding fixing up of the final product. Fresh ash leachates of volcanic ash which is high in sulphur (comparison is justified below) are found readily soluble and pH varied highly. However, the ash from the later phase of the eruption was more acidic, with a pH of approximately 5.1. The contribution to the pH obtained in the drug and contribution to the water soluble extractive from the percentage of minerals other than the primary ingredient sulphur and from the phytochemicals need to be explored and compared. If the contributing factor is mineral the shelf life would be as expected and there would be meagre chances of immediate deterioration. Otherwise, if from phytochemicals (oxygenated compounds) then chances of contamination is comparatively higher. The importance of extent of care during storage of Gandaka karuppu is dealt here based on pH.

Ashing involves an oxidation of the components of the product. A high ash value is indicative of contamination, substitution, adulteration or carelessness in preparing the crude drug for marketing [17, 21]. The total ash usually consists of carbonates, phosphates, silicates and silica which include both physiological ash (plant tissue) and non-physiological ash (environmental contamination such as sand and soil) [17, 22, and 23]. The total ash observed in the siddha drug is 16.40%. Physiological ash interferes with the illustration of total ash in reflecting the quality of herbal medicines e.g. Calcium oxalate. Thus the Acid insoluble ash also establish the quality of Siddha herbal formulation. The high Acid insoluble ash might be due to the addition of Sulphur and the other minerals in other ingredients of the formulation. The water-soluble extractive value denotes the presence of phytochemicals such as sugar & acids and inorganic compounds. The water soluble extractive value in the present Siddha compound formulation found be 4.2% indicated some water soluble components in the formulation. Clinically the drug showed better improvement for the treatment of the Skin disease (unpublished data and in experience). The acid radicals present were sulphate, chloride, carbonate, fluoride. This result is in agreement with all the major species of acid radicals detected in fresh ash leachates of volcanic ash (Witham et al., 2006) [24] and carbonates from phyto components of the drug. The basic radicals present were iron and ammonium. The volcanic ash is high in sulphur content and is of traditional and pharmaceutical importance that Volcanic Earth *Healing Centre Spa* (<http://www.volcanicearth.com>) emerged and uses the ash extensively and quotes that the Sulphur in Volcanic Ash is a proven, safe, age-old remedy that has been used to treat every conceivable skin irritation and infection.

Transformation of sulphur to biosulphur during the heat processing of drug with other herbal ingredients (pudam) to render the elemental sulphur to be partly hydrophilic need to be analyzed in forthcoming studies. This hydrophilic nature might be responsible for the efficacious activity of the drug clinically as indicated in the classical text for skin diseases. More than the direct solubility, the rate of solution, dissolution and the respective pH would provide predictive results in future to know the fate of purified and processed sulphur through Siddha traditional methods, in the drug in case of preliminary tests.

Standardization ensure the safety of drugs through limit tests for heavy metals. Though this study does not include the parameter, some sulphur based literary siddha research evidences support the safety of the drug GK and is proven to be low toxic [12]. Poorna Cantirota Centuram is prepared with gold, mercury, and sulphur (major ingredient). The drug is reported that it can be classified as Category 5 with low acute toxicity hazard. In both acute and repeated dose toxicity studies, the drug showed no significant adverse effects. The research evidences regarding the proven safety of the Siddha formulation Rasagandhi Mezhugu (RGM), with sulphur as one of the ingredients is documented [25]. These sulphur based safety of non- karuppu dosage forms support the safety of Gandhaka karuppu too. In specific acute toxicity of Gandaga karuppu has proved to be non toxic (D. Deepa Bai., et al – to be published soon). Vasambu karukku is a herbal karuppu paediatric dosage form [26]. This karukku is the purified form of the drug [27].

In spite of improvements in science, identification of the potency is still based on traditional methods [28]. The indication of the drug GK, recommended to be administered with the melted cow's ghee is either to disperse the supposed nano particulate drug by hot melt method [29] or improve the miscibility to enhance the acceptability and efficacy of the drug. The cow's ghee which serve both as a vehicle and an adjuvant guide to expect that the constituents in the final product to be thermo-stable in the melted form of ghee. The role of supercritical CO₂ and the necessary conditions that fit in the processing of Gandaka Karuppu, are discussed as the solubility enhancer [30] and efficacy enhancer in the drug (Deepa Bai et al- to be published soon). The sustained availability of genuine raw materials improves the quality and effectiveness of traditional medicines in the present world of cost effectiveness, adulterated, substituted and controversial drugs [31]. The ingredients of GK Siddha medicine are commonly available at reliable cost.

In specific, a comparative TLC of the drug with that of the 'Thin Layer Chromatographic Atlas of Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeial Drugs' for piper nigrum [32] and comparative TLC of other herbal ingredients from other pharmacopoeias would be an updated study and an immediate requirement to complete the preliminary standardization of Gandaka karuppu.

CONCLUSION

The physico-chemical standardization authenticate the finished Siddha herbo mineral product to be of acceptable and standard quality and is devoid of adulterants. The results of this study may be used as the reference standard in further research undertakings of its kind and thus fulfilling the scope of Knowledge based medicinal products (Dr. Handa's statement) [33].

Future research

Standardization and quality control with integrated traditional knowledge and modern scientific techniques is important [34]. Since this is the first documentation on the drug Gandhaga karuppu for its authenticity, advanced analytical techniques like 1. SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy), AFM (Atomic Force Microscopy) studies are needed to validate the fact involved in solubility/adsorptive capability of sulphur 2. Preliminary sieving tests and particle size analysis and compare the grinding time of karuppu and confirm the micronisation, 3. X-ray Diffraction studies to identify the crystalline phases in the processed sulphur and functional group identification techniques like IR and NMR [35] with an expectation for the functional groups to cleave the disulphide bonds of hyperkeratinised cells and improve this Siddha medicine as scientifically validated potent drug for the treating the skin diseases and for other indications mentioned in the classical text.

The processed and supposed bio-sulphur may be tried to use it commercially as biofuel, bio-fertilizer. AAS (Atomic absorption studies) are also essential for the confirmation of percentage of minerals. Phytochemical studies, assay of active ingredients in Gandhaga karuppu, quantification through HPLC and HPTLC [36] are further required.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am highly privileged to acknowledge with thanks to Prof. Dr. Ramaswamy, DG, CCRS Chennai-106 for their encouragement. I express my thanks to my Supervisor Dr. M. Allimuthu M.D (Siddha), former Head of the Department of Gunapadam Branch, for his valuable guidance throughout the study. I also thank to Dr. Jayanthi Athikkal (PSO-Phg.), PCIM&H, Ghaziabad and Dr. Sathyarajeswaran parameswaran Director, i/c, SCRI, DR. Shyamala Raj kumar (RO), CCRS, for their extended kind support. I also thank Mr. Rajneesh Kumar, Dr. Suda Revathy Sendilkumar and Mr. Sendilkumar for their timely help. I thank all the staff members of both the institutes for their cooperation.

I gratefully acknowledge my sincere thanks to The TN Dr. MGR Medical University, Guindy, Chennai - 600032 and our former principal Dr. Khadhar, Govt Siddha Medical College, Chennai-106.

Declaration

There is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Tambekar D.H., Dahikar S.B., Lahare M.D., "Antibacterial potentials of some herbal preparations available in India", *Res J Med Med Sci* 2009; 4:224; 7.
2. Chattopadhyay R.R., Bhattacharyya S.K., *Terminalia chebula*: An update. *Pharmacogn Rev* 2007; 1:151;6
3. Siddha maruthuva Chikitcha saaram, Page no 108 & 109.
4. Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani medicines by PLIM, Ghaziabad under the department of AYUSH, Ministry of Health and Family welfare, New Delhi.
5. Anonymous. Quality Control Methods for Medicinal Plant Materials, World Health Organisation, Geneva; 1998.
6. Protocol for testing of Ayurvedic, Siddha and Unani medicines, PLIM, Ghaziabad, MHFW, Department of AYUSH; 2007.
7. Raman N. Phytochemical technique: New Indian publishing agencies: New Delhi (2006);19
8. Rabe. T and Staden J.V, Antibacterial activity of South African plants used in medicinal purposes, *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 1997; 56: 81 – 87.
9. Atta – ur – Rahman et al, Antifungal diterpenoid alkaloids from *Delphinium denudatum*, *J.Nat. Prod*; 1997, 60: 472 – 474.
10. Prasanta Kumar Sarkar, Neky J. Mehta, P. K. Prajapati. Chemistry of Kupipakwa Rasayanas - A Review. *Ancient Science of Life* April, May, June - 2008; Vol: No.XXVII (4):1 - 7
11. Kulkarni DA. Vagbhata's Rasaratnasamuchchaya. New Delhi: Meharchanda Lachmandas Publication; 2010. 8/5; 145.
12. V.Velpandian, M.Pitchiah Kumar, N.Anbu, Md.Musthafa , K. Kanakavalli., Clinical Evaluation of Siddha Drug Gowri Chinthamani Chendooram in the Management of Osteoarthritis, *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science Invention*, Volume 2, Issue 1 , January 2013, 26-32.
13. Anonymous, Indian Pharmacopoeia-Vol III. Controller of Publications, Ghaziabad 2007; 2034-2057.
14. Rakesh S Shivatare, Ashish S Pande, Hanumant U Bhusnar, Prasad V Kadam, Kavita N Yadav, Manohar J Patil. Standardization of Narasimha Churna: A Poly-Herbal Formulation, *Asian Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2013; 3: (23), 23-27.
15. Anonymous, The Siddha Formulary of India, Part I, (English), Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt of India, 1992; 153.
16. Law relating to drugs and cosmetics, 25th ed with supplement, EBC Publishing (P) Ltd., Lucknow – 26001, 2016 S-24.
17. Mukherjee PK. Quality control of herbal drugs. 1st ed. Business Horizons Publishers, New Delhi 2003; 97- 98,184-195, 248- 249, 529-567, 701-725, 750-766.
18. Marcelo Gonzaga de Freitas Araújo and Taís Maria Bauab, Microbial Quality of Medicinal Plant Materials, Latest Research into Quality Control Chapter-4, 72
19. Liu, X., Qiu, Z., Wang, L., & Chen, Y. (2011). Quality evaluation of *Panax notoginseng* extract dried by different drying methods. *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, 89, 10-14.
20. Abba, D., Inabo, H. I., Yakubu, S. E., & Olonitola, O. S. (2009). Contamination of herbal medicinal products marketed in Kaduna Metropolis with selected pathogenic bacteria. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 6, 70-77.
21. World Health Organization (WHO). Quality Control Methods for Medicinal Plant Materials. AITBS Publishers, Delhi 2002; 46-51.
22. Evans WC. Trease and Evan's Pharmacognosy. 15th ed. Saunders Company Limited Publishers, London 2002; 98-99.
23. Yulan Rao and Bingren XIANG, Determination of Total Ash and Acid- insoluble Ash of Chinese Herbal Medicine *Prunellae Spica* by Near Infrared Spectroscopy, *Yakugaku zasshi* 129(7) 881-886(2009).
24. Anonymous, Final report on eqc research contract 10/sp607: 'A quantitative analysis Of volcanic ash damage to new zealand roof structures and materials', University of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand, 20 July 2011, 9.
25. B. Chitra, R. S. Ramaswamy, and V. Suba, Toxicity Evaluation of Pūrṇa Cantiroṭaya Centūram, a Siddha Medicine in Wistar Rats, *International Scholarly Research Notices*, Volume 2015 (2015), Article ID 473296.
26. Child care in siddha- An overview, Sathiya rajeswaran.P1, Kiruthiga.G2, Patturayan.R3& Anandan.T4. <http://siddharesearch.blogspot.in/2011/07/child-care-in-siddha-overview-sathiya.html>.
27. Anonymous, The Siddha Formulary of India, Part II, (Tamil), Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt of India, 1992; 382.
28. Sharad D. Pawar, Sonali Goraniya, Nayana Tusamda, Amey R. Shirolkar, Gajendra Rao, S. N. Murthy, Molecular Analysis Of Manilkara Hexandra Roxb. And Averrhoa Carambola L.Using Rapd Markers Helps To Understand Genetic Variations, *International Journal Of Pharmacy And Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2013; Vol 5, Suppl 3, Issn - 0975-1491.
29. Ketan T. Savjani, Anuradha K. Gajjar, and Jignasa K. Savjani, Drug Solubility: Importance and Enhancement Techniques, *ISRN Pharm.* 2012; 2012: 195727, (PMC99483), 3.
30. DongshengWen, H.Jiang, KaiZhang, Supercritical fluids technology for clean biofuel production, *Progress in Natural Science*, Volume 19, Issue 3, 10 March 2009, 274.
31. Shyamala Rajkumar, V. Vijaya Kumar, G. Masilamani, Sasikala ethirajulu and T. Anandan, Controversial identity of some medicinal plants in Siddha medicine, *Journal of Siddha* Vol : 2, Issue : 2, 2009, 31.
32. Anonymous, Thin Layer Chromatographic Atlas of Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeial Drugs, Part I, Volume III, First ed, published on behalf of Govt of India by Pharmacopoeia Commission of Indian Medicine and Homoeopathy, Ghaziabad-201002, Uttar Pradesh, India, 52.
33. A K S Rawat, J K Johri & P Pushpangadan, Quality control and standardization of traditional medicine A report *Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research* , Vol. 64, March 2005, 229-233.

34. Jitendra D. Bhosale , Amey R. Shirolkar , Umesh D. Pete ,Chetan M. Zade , Dipesh P. Mahajan, Chakradhar D. Hadole, Sharad D. Pawar et al, Synthesis, characterization and biological activities of novel substituted formazans of 3,4-dimethyl-1Hpyrrole-2-carbohydrazide derivatives, Journal of pharmacy research7, 201; 582-587.
35. Sharad D. Pawar, Chinmay S. Mulye, Amey R. Shirolkar, Bishnupriya Dhar, S.Murthy, Rapd-Pcr Analysis Of Bixa Orellana L. And Salacia Chinens L.To Study Genetic Diversity, International Journal Of Advanced Biotechnology And Research, Issn 0976-2612, Online Issn 2278-599x, Vol 4, Issue 3, 2013; 380-383.
36. Subash Chandra Verma, Rachana Rani, Pramila Pant, M. M. Padhi, C. L. Jain, Ramesh Babu Quantitative determination of ferulic acid in Ricinus communis Linn. leaves and its geographical variation using HPTLC fingerprint, Der Chemica Sinica, 2011; Vol. 2 (5), 127-135.

54878478451170545

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

